

EFFECT OF MICROSTRUCTURAL INHOMOGENEITY ON THE STRENGTH OF PARTICULATE METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The clustering of particles in metal matrix composite systems is known to affect damage and fracture behaviour. Recent experimental work suggests that it also affects the plasticity at small strains. In this paper we review the existing experimental and numerical modelling work in this area. We present a model which addresses the influence of clustering on initial yield and strain hardening. Finally, some model experiments which aim to show the effect more conclusively will be described. These experiments involve the use of atomized powder having intentionally different compositions, which enables the development of a bimodal distribution of the reinforcing phase on a scale of about one order of magnitude greater than the particle size.

INTRODUCTION

All natural and man-made solid state materials contain structural features with characteristic length scales spanning several orders of magnitude, ranging from the inter-atomic spacing to naturally occurring and processing induced disparities such as cracks and pores. In the case of multi-phase inorganic composites, the characteristic length scale of features such as the reinforcement size, aspect ratio, spacing and local volume fraction may be distributed over large scales such that descriptions of composite microstructures by average quantities is physically inappropriate. Figure 1 illustrates two microstructures of an identical Al alloy (Alcan A356 containing 20 vol. % SiC) particulate metal matrix composite (PMMC) cooled at different rates from the melt [1]. The slowly cooled investment cast alloy forms dense clusters of SiC particles segregated to the Si-rich interdendritic phase of the alloy.

Microstructural inhomogeneity on the scale of the reinforcing phase is typical of PMMC's, and for the length scales of reinforcing phases which we will consider in this paper (between 0.1-100 μm), the disorder is often labelled "mesoscopic" to distinguish it from other characteristic scales of inhomogeneity [2] (we shall use the terms "disorder" and "inhomogeneous" synonymously in this paper). This raises a number of questions regarding the relative contribution of each microstructural element to the macroscopic mechanical response. For example, modern constitutive equations for crystal plasticity require the specification of a unique length scale (for the case of metal polycrystals, the average grain size) [3]. If we accept that composites are disordered on the mesoscopic level, how do we practically sum the responses of microstructural

features distributed over a large length scale? The focus of this paper will be effect of disorder on the elasticity, yield and damage of PMMC's, as well as computational and experimental challenges to simulating the constitutive behaviour of disordered microstructures.

INHOMOGENEITY EFFECTS ON THE MECHANICAL RESPONSE

ELASTIC RESPONSE

A large body of literature is devoted to the problem of predicting the effective elastic properties of multiphase materials, and excellent reviews of the subject of composite elasticity are available in the literature [4-6]. The elastic properties of two phase composites are bounded above and below by the Voigt (equal strain partitioning) and Reuss (equal stress partitioning) approximations, and for the case of equiaxed particles, bounds are given by variational principles elucidated by Hashin [7].

Figure 1. Microstructures of A356/20 Vol. % SiC PMMC's obtained by a) Investment Casting and b) Pressure Die Casting [1].

A number of different computational strategies for the calculation of narrower bounds on the elastic properties of inhomogeneous media have been proposed based on the continuum mechanics of ellipsoidal inclusions pioneered by Eshelby [8]. The original formulation of the problem by Eshelby calculates the strain field outside of an inclusion embedded within an *infinite matrix* (ie. the inclusion "samples" the elastic properties of the softer matrix phase only), yielding excellent approximations of the effective elastic properties of dilute concentrations of particles. For higher volume fractions, elastic interactions between groups of particles become important. A number of variants of "finite Eshelby" methods (or "Effective Medium Approximations") are given in the literature which correct for particle-particle interactions. A popular method is the self-consistent method [10] which yields good approximations of the elastic behaviour in a number of PMMC systems [11]. We shall not derive the solution here, but the effective stiffness of a composite C_c^* containing a volume fraction f of a hard elastic phase with an average stiffness C_i in a matrix with and effective stiffness C_m^* is given by solving for the positive root of the quadratic expression

$$\alpha(C_c^*)^2 + [(\beta-\gamma)fC_i + (\beta-\gamma(1-f))C_m^*]C_c^* - \beta C_i C_m^* = 0 \quad (1)$$

where the constants α , β and γ are functions of the Poissons ratio of the matrix and inclusion.

The self-consistent method yields excellent approximations for a number of Al based PMMC systems as shown in Figure 2.

For microstructural scales typical of PMMC systems, the choice of scale independent continuum methods such as the EMA analysis is appropriate. On the other hand, spatial variations in stiffness are to be expected in real PMMC's due to inhomogeneous distribution of the reinforcing phase, as particle dense regions spanning scales on the order of many particle diameters should be expected to behave stiffer than the overall composite. Although we expect this second order effect to be small, it is nonetheless neglected by homogenization techniques such as EMA. A scheme to calculate the effective elastic properties of composites based on experimentally obtained stereological input has been proposed [12], although it is unclear if this method offers significant advantages over conventional techniques already well established in the literature.

Figure 2. Analytical predictions of the elastic modulus of Al-SiC PMMC's vs. measured values of various alloy systems [11].

INELASTIC RESPONSE

Elastic stress partitioning to the inclusions will continue so long as it is not energetically favourable to activate an energy dissipation process, during which the composite departs from linear elastic behaviour. Of concern to us are the relaxation processes which dominate room-temperature mechanical behaviour, namely plastic deformation of the matrix phase and fracture and decohesion of the elastic inclusions. Thus, the post-yield strain hardening behaviour of PMMC's will be dominated by two terms: i) a contribution proportional to the elastic modulus multiplied by the volume fraction of undamaged reinforcing phase, and ii) a contribution proportional to the square root of the instantaneous dislocation density within the matrix, characteristic of stage II hardening of pure metallic polycrystals.

Superposition of the two hardening terms is difficult, and it is not obvious which term dominates the hardening behaviour at a given strain. We discuss matrix plasticity and particle damage separately below.

Yield Behaviour and the Elastic-Plastic Transition

The yield stress in metal polycrystals is conventionally defined by a constant offset strain from the elastic limit (usually 0.2 percent). On the other hand, permanent offsets in PMMC's have

been measured at strains of 10^{-5} and below [13-15]. This complicates the interpretation of PMMC strength since the point at which "general" yielding occurs (ie. the point at which dislocation activity is occurring throughout the volume of the sample) in the material is not well defined. Consequently, comparisons of the stress developed in the composite with that of the unreinforced matrix alloy at comparable applied strains is a matter of debate for reasons discussed below.

Partitioning of the strains between the matrix and reinforcement complicates interpretation of the yield curve, since dislocation activity will in general be inhomogeneously nucleated throughout the microstructure according to spatial variations of the deviatoric stress. Departure from linear elastic behaviour at small strains may only indicate the initiation of highly localized plasticity in a small volume of the test specimen. Slip line visualization experiments by Corbin [13] do indeed suggest that plasticity is highly inhomogeneous in this small strain regime. Pragnell et. al. [15] proposes that information obtained from higher derivatives of the strain hardening curve may be used to interpret the initial onset of plasticity at a local level (specifically, the minimum of the third derivative).

Thermal residual stresses due to CTE mismatch between the matrix and reinforcement may lead to tensile-compressive yield asymmetries during testing. Finite element (FEM) models of the residual stress state induced by cooling Al based composite systems typically predict compressive residual stresses [16-18], and the effect of residual stresses on the initial yielding behaviour is complicated by particle shape (most notably the aspect ratio) and particle distribution effects. Yield asymmetries in a number of Al based PMMC systems have now been observed at small plastic strains [13,14].

The elastic-plastic transition and the development of strength in an Al based PMMC has been modelled [11] using an incremental form of equation 1 similar to a form used by Chen and Argon to model power law creep of a multi-phase material [19], in which the instantaneous effective modulus of the matrix C_m^* is assumed to be the instantaneous "tangent" modulus of the unreinforced alloy at an equivalent applied strain. Figure 3 compares the results of experimentally determined PMMC flow curves with the incremental self-consistent model. The model tends to underpredict the flow stress of the PMMC. The effect of inhomogeneous particle distribution may be modelled [11] by estimating the tangent modulus of "lean" and "rich" phases using a modified Ramberg-Osgood flow equation [20,21]. The model predicts a stronger response in the inhomogeneous composites and is more consistent with experiment.

Figure 3. Experimental flow curves of two A356 Al alloy-SiC PMMC's (T61) vs. Prediction by incremental self-consistent model [13].

Damage Accumulation and Fracture

Most studies of inhomogeneity effects in PMMC's have concentrated on damage accumulation and fracture. FEM simulations have demonstrated the hydrostatic component of the stress state in matrix material sandwiched between closely spaced particles is a strong function of the interparticle spacing [22-25], which implies that these regions are likely to be most susceptible to damage. Experimental observations support this view [26-29], although there is some misunderstanding as to whether the hydrostatic stresses nucleate voids in virgin material or in processing induced flaws correlated with higher local densities of particles [29]. Experimental evidence also suggests that damage increases linearly with strain and is initiated preferentially at larger particles [30], consistent with the view that larger particles fracture due to the presence of surface flaws of scale proportional to the size of the particle.

A MESOSCOPIC INTERPRETATION OF PMMC YIELDING

AN OUTLINE OF A CONSTITUTIVE MODEL

The word "disorder" used in the context of this paper implies the absence of periodicity, or the lack of a single characteristic scale length representative of the entire structure. We have given examples of a number of physical processes which occur during loading which are sensitive to local fluctuations in the mesoscopic microstructural scale. On the other hand, most FEM models of PMMC behaviour model the microstructural geometry by a single "unit cell" (often a single particle surrounded by a ductile matrix phase) assuming periodic boundary conditions. Although there are a few notable exceptions [18,24,31], limitations on data storage limit the volume of material that may be practically simulated. Although these models yield detailed information on the stress fields at small distances away from the inclusion-matrix interface, a large number of FEM simulations would be required to take into account the effects of reinforcement shape, volume fraction, aspect ratio and reinforcement distribution.

The simplest model of disorder is to replace the concept of a single average representative scale length (such as crack length, grain diameter, particle size, interparticle spacing etc.) with a scale distribution function, the form of which represents the number density of microstructural features of scale λ within a representative volume of the microstructure. If we designate $f(\lambda)$ to represent a length scale probability density, we may write:

$$\int_0^{\lambda_m} f(\lambda) d\lambda = 1 \quad (2)$$

where 0 and λ_m are defined as the extreme values of the distribution. The moment $\langle \lambda^n \rangle$ is defined as

$$\langle \lambda^n \rangle = \int_0^{\lambda_m} \lambda^n f(\lambda) d\lambda \quad (3)$$

Having defined the above property of the distribution, it is germane to consider the following questions: i) are the yield, flow and fracture behaviour of PMMC's governed by higher moments of the distribution function (ie. $n > 1$), and ii) what is the moment? Although we considered experimental evidence in the previous sections which suggest that, at least in the case of damage, the damage accumulation rate of PMMC's is sensitive to the shape of the particle size

distribution, we suspect that disorder strongly influences the elastic-plastic transition as well. Specifically, the hydrostatic component of the stress state is likely to dominate the post-yield hardening curve at low strains, especially in regions of high local volume fraction. These regions are more likely to store elastic energy due to the difficulty in initiating plastic flow due local constraints within the inter-particle regions. On the other hand, these regions are also more likely to see particles fracture because of the hydrostatic stresses which develop there during straining.

We speculate that the elastic-plastic transition in PMMC's can be interpreted as a percolation process. Dislocation activity is likely to be initiated first in regions which are relatively particle free. This corresponds to the extreme value of a scale distribution function, where the scale represents the local particle spacing in this case. Deforming regions will then percolate throughout the microstructure by progressively sampling "harder" regions of the composite (ie. regions of higher particle density). We feel that our speculation is justified by analogy to well established constitutive models: specifically, there is a large body of literature devoted to "exhaustion" models of transient creep and recovery [32-33] of alloys based on the heuristic that flowing glide dislocations sample "weak" regions of the dislocation forest (ie. regions of lowest activation energy flow first), and proceed to sample denser and denser regions of the forest as deformation proceeds forward.

EXPERIMENTAL APPROACH

We wish to quantify through experiment the extent to which reinforcement distribution effects effect the elastic-plastic transition. There is currently a lack of good experimental investigations of inhomogeneity effects due to the inherent difficulty of *a priori* control over the spatial distribution of the reinforcing phase. Since current processing methods of PMMC's allow little control over the distribution, we have investigated a novel procedure for making model PMMC's via powder metallurgy of an in-situ two-phase alloy based on the Al-Cu system.

We have obtained spherical gas-atomized metal alloy pellets of Al-Cu alloys (courtesy of Prof. H. Henien, University of Alberta) based on the Al-Cu eutectic system. An example of the powder microstructures is shown in Figure 4. The alloy is an ideal model composite system,

Figure 4. Microstructure of atomized Al-17 wt. % Cu alloy. Dark phase is Al_2Cu .

comprised of a ductile Al-Cu solid solution and a hard, brittle intermetallic phase Al_2Cu . Since the eutectic is composed of 50 vol. % of Al_2Cu , compositions over a wide range of volume fractions are available for study. A homogeneous composite may be produced by consolidating pellets of uniform composition (eg. the alloy Al-17 wt.% Cu contains 20 vol. % of the intermetallic phase Al_2Cu). The same alloy may be produced by consolidating a mixture of pellets, with the overall composition is maintained (eg. a 50:50 mixture of Al-24 wt.% Cu and Al-10 wt.% Cu). The second technique would generate a bimodal distribution of particles. Blending powders of different compositions will allow us to generate microstructures of varying inhomogeneity for testing.

SUMMARY

Standard processing methods of PMMC's lead to inhomogeneous microstructures on the mesoscopic scale. At all levels of strain, we expect the mechanical properties to be a function of the level of inhomogeneity, especially in the post-yield mechanical response. Although most experiments have concentrated on inhomogeneity effects on damage and fracture, few studies have been undertaken to examine the effect on yield and strain hardening. We propose a novel method for the production of model PMMC's which allow a priori control of the reinforcement distribution.

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